

DEVELOPMENT OF NANOFIBER REINFORCED TRANSPARENT COMPOSITES

Zheng-Ming Huang, Xiao-fei Wang, Lu-song Chen
School of Aerospace Engineering & Applied Mechanics,
Tongji University, 1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, P. R. China
Tel.: +86-(0)21-65985373; Fax: +86-(0)21-65985373;
E-mail: huangzm@mail.tongji.edu.cn

SUMMARY

This paper focuses on application of co-axial electrospinning technique to the development of nanofiber reinforced transparent composites. Investigations have been done on fabrication and functionalization of the transparent composites with improved mechanical properties, thermal properties and shielding ability for ultraviolet radiations. In the fabrication, PMMA, a polymer with excellent visible light transmittance, is chosen as shell part of the co-axial composite nanofibers, whereas PA-6 with higher melting temperature and better mechanical performance is utilized as core part of the nanofibers. Under proper processing temperature, the shell part of the composite nanofibers melts and forms a resin matrix, whereas the core part maintains original fiber topology and plays a reinforcing role in the resin matrix. In this work, the influence of different contents of the core nanofibers on mechanical properties, thermal properties and visible light transmittance of the transparent composites is investigated. Further investigations are related with functionalization on the transparent composites. After a special treatment, TiO₂ nano-particles are added into either the shell or the core part of the electrospun nanofibers, whereas MWCNTs are introduced only into the core nanofibers. These particles are blended with respective polymer solutions before co-axial electrospinning. The resulting core-shell composite nanofibers with the additives are then hot pressed into the nanofiber and the nano additive reinforced composites, which are characterized to study the influence of the additives and their content on the mechanical, thermal, visible light transmittance, and anti-ultraviolet light transmittance performance of the composites. The results indicate that with a minor loss of less than 10% in transparency, the tensile modulus and tensile strength of the transparent PMMA composites can be increased by around 20% higher than the counterparts of the pure PMMA organic glass. The TiO₂ nano-particles added in the shell part of the electrospun composite nanofibers exhibit a remarkable performance on UV light transmittance of the transparent composites but lower down visible light transmittance to a relatively large extent. On the contrary, those added in the core part had a reversed effect on anti-UV light performance and on visible light transmittance. A proper amount of MWCNTs added into the PA-6 core can result in a further increase in the mechanical properties of the transparent composites.

Key words: Co-axial electrospinning, nanofiber reinforcement, transparency,

1. INTRODUCTION

Mechanical reinforcements on optically transparent polymers have attracted a great deal of attention in a wide range of applications such as optical instruments, architecture, aerospace and agriculture [1]. However, if refractive indexes of the fillers and the polymer are unmatched, the resulting composite becomes opaque or non-transparent due to light scattering. The refractive indexes of polymer and fillers vary with environment variables [2, 3]. Previous work has indicated that the composite loses its transparency with an increase in fiber content. This is attributed to the mismatching of refractive index enhanced [4, 5, 6]. In order to improve the mechanical properties and at the same time to result in a low loss of transparency, one possible way would be to use fillers with a diameter significantly smaller than the wave length of a visible light [3]. Nanofillers are believed to have a potential to substantially improve polymer mechanical properties at very low filler loadings. Their large interfacial area enables an applied load to be transferred through filler/matrix interface [7, 8].

Functional particles, such as TiO₂, have been studied for applications as a catalyst and UV absorber [9, 10, 11]. Some researches have shown that the shielding ability for ultraviolet radiations is relevant to the diameter of particles. A smaller diameter of the TiO₂ particles shows a better UV shielding ability. However, under certain experimental conditions, TiO₂ nanoparticles have a strong tendency to agglomerate into larger particles, thus maybe decrease the functionality.

Electrospinning is one of the simplest methods to fabricate nanofibers. Using electrospun nanofiber membrane to reinforce a transparent polymer resin with enhanced mechanical properties and low loss of transparency has been reported [3, 6]. In our work, a coaxial electrospinning method was used to fabricate PMMA/PA6 composite nanofibers, which were further hot pressed into PA6 nanofiber reinforced PMMA transparent composites. Other nanofillers such as TiO₂ nanoparticles and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) were introduced by adding the fillers into a polymer liquid before the co-axial electrospinning to further improve overall behaviors of the composites. Our results demonstrated that the new nanocomposites could remarkably enhance mechanical and other relevant properties with low lost in transparency.

2. EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

Poly (methyl methacrylate) was purchased from LG Chemical Industrial Ltd, whereas PA6 was provided by Shanghai elite plastic CO., Ltd. TiO₂ nanoparticles and MWCNTs were obtained from Nano-Science & Technology Research Center of Shanghai University and Shenzhen Nanotechnologies Co. Ltd., respectively. The average particle

size of TiO₂ was less than 50nm, and the MWCNTs were 10~20 nm in diameter and about 5~10µm in length. TFE (2, 2, 2-Trifluoroethanol), a solvent for the PMMA and PA6, was provided by Shanghai chemical reagent CO., Ltd. A surface treatment was made before the Nanoparticles (TiO₂, MWCNTs) were added.

2.2 Fabrication

PA-6 core and PMMA shell composite nanofiber membranes were obtained in terms of coaxial electrospinning [12]. Four loading contents namely 0.8%, 2.5%, 4.1% and 5.9% of PA-6 in the PA-6/PMMA composite membranes were investigated in this work, which were obtained by adjusting mass concentrations in the PA-6 solutions and flow rates. In addition, the weight contents of the TiO₂ in the composite membranes were 0%, 0.5%, 1%, 1.5% and 2.0% whereas those of the MWCNTs were 0%, 0.05%, 0.1%, 0.3%, 0.5%, and 1.0% respectively.

A stainless steel mold was used to fabricate PA-6 nanofiber reinforced PMMA transparent composites. The composite nanofiber membranes were carefully laid up into the mold, which was put within a hot press chamber. The heating temperature on the mold was set to about 190⁰C, which was higher than the melting temperature of PMMA but lower than that of PA-6, and a pressure of 2MPa was applied. After the mold was cooled down at room temperature and was opened, a nanofiber reinforced transparent composite was obtained.

2.3 Characterization

The core-shell structure and the nanofiller distribution were examined by TEM (HITACHI H-800 type) at 100 KV. Surface topography and diameter of the composite nanofibers were viewed with SEM (HITACHI S-2360N) at 15 kV. The composite nanofibers were analyzed qualitatively by FTIR (Bruker EQUINOX 55 type). TGA tests were performed on a STA449C thermal analyzer (NETZSCH Company, Germany) using a constant heating rate of 20°C/min.

Mechanical behavior of the nanofiber reinforced composites was characterized through tensile test on a small-size tester (Model CSS-44020 Changchun research institute for testing machines, China), with sample sizes of 100mm×15mm×1.5mm and a loading velocity of 3mm/min.

760CRT twin beam ultraviolet visible complementary filter (Shanghai Cany Precision Instruments Co., Ltd.) was employed to determine light transmittance of the nanofiber reinforced transparent composites, in a wavelength region of 200-850nm.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Nanofiber Morphology

Fig. 1 shows SEM images of the electrospun PMMA/PA-6, PMMA/PA-6 (TiO₂), PMMA/PA-6 (MWCNTs) nanofibers, respectively. Diameters of the PMMA/PA-6 nanofibers were slightly increased with increasing PA-6 concentrations, and fiber surface morphology was smooth without any beads [Fig. 1(a, b)]. **Fig. 2(a)** presents TEM images of the electrospun PMMA/PA-6 nanofibers, which exhibited a sharp edged core/shell structure along the fiber axis, with an outer diameter of about 400±80 nm and a wall thickness of about 75±25 nm. When the nanofibers were treated with UV, it seemed that the core/shell became a single phase structure (**Fig. 2(b)**).

The fabrication of the TiO₂ (or MWCNTs)-PMMA/PA-6 composites was achieved by adding the nanoparticles into either the PMMA or the PA-6 solution (MWCNTs added in only the PA-6 solution). Typical SEM images of PMMA/PA-6/TiO₂ and PMMA/PA-6/MWCNTs nanofibers were illustrated in **Fig 1(b, c)** and **Fig 1(d)**, respectively. There were many beads in the PMMA/PA-6/TiO₂ fibers no matter how much amount of TiO₂ was added in the core or the shell part. TEM pictures show that some TiO₂ particles also occurred in the other part of the core/shell composite nanofibers, in addition to the primary part as shown in Fig 2(c, d). This was attributed to the aggregation of some TiO₂ particles in the solution. During electrospinning, the agglomerated nano particles were difficult to split into thinner fibers, and formed beads on the fiber surface. This phenomenon was not observed in the electrospun PMMA/PA-6/MWCNTs nanofibers, indicating that MWCNTs were dispersed well in the corresponding solution or an aggregation was easy to be detached under the electric force.

Fig. 1 SEM photos of PMMA/PA-6 nanofibers (a) original, (b) 1.5% TiO₂ added in the shell part, (c) 1.5% TiO₂ added in the core part, and (d) 1% MWCNTs added in the core part

Fig. 2 TEM photos of PMMA/PA-6 nanofibers, a): original, b): treated with UV for 60min, c): 1.5% TiO₂ added in the shell part, d): 1.5% TiO₂ added in the core part

3.2 FTIR and Thermal Behavior

Infrared spectrums of pure PA-6, pure PMMA and PMMA/PA-6 composite materials are shown in **Fig 3**. The composite had primary characteristic peaks of both PMMA and PA6. Thermal stability of the composite was improved slightly with increasing PA-6 content in the nanofibers (**Fig 4**).

Fig 3 FT-IR spectrum of PMMA, PA-6 and PA-6 core-PMMA shell nanofibers

3.3 Composite Transmittance

Transmittances of the PMMA/PA-6 nanocomposites dropped down in the wavelength range between 350-900nm with an increase in the PA-6 content, as shown in **Fig 5**. There was a slightly decreased transparency (less than 10%) with 0.8% mass percent of PA-6 added compared with that of pure PMMA. However, sharp drop occurred with

further increasing the PA-6 nanofiber content. The reason was that more nanofibers in the composite, with larger diameters, inevitably blocked the transmittance of a visible light, and a less transmittance was induced.

Fig 4 DSC curves of a) pure PMMA panel, b) PMMA/PA-6 composite with 1.5% PA-6, and c) PMMA/PA-6 composite with 3% PA-6

To study the optical properties of the PMMA/PA-6/TiO₂ and PMMA/PA-6/MWCNTs composites, their transmittances at different mass percentages of the particles were obtained (**Figs 6 and 7**). For the PMMA/PA-6/TiO₂ composite, a main absorption of TiO₂ was strong in the wavelength range of 230-400 nm. The TiO₂ nano-particles added in the shell part of the electrospun composite nanofibers exhibited a remarkable performance on absorbing UV lights, but a low transmittance to a visible light. On the contrary, those added in the core part had a reversed effect on anti-UV light performance and on visible transmittance light. Our experiment showed that the transparency of both the PMMA/PA-6/TiO₂ and PMMA/PA-6/MWCNTs composites fell down with increasing the mass percentage of the nanoparticles.

3.4 Mechanical Characterization

Figs 8, 9, and 10 show mechanical properties of the PA-6 nanofiber reinforced transparent composites. The tensile strength increased substantially with an increase in PA-6 nanofiber content. Tensile modulus was also increased, as shown in **Fig 8**. When the PA-6 nanofiber content was within the range of 2.5~5.9%, the resulting composites achieved a maximum strength and modulus with an increase of 36.5% in the strength and 13.3% in the modulus, compared to a pure PMMA panel made by the similar processing method. The results suggest that the nanofibers provided an effective reinforcement. The intermolecular forces between the PA-6 nanofibers and the PMMA matrix might enhance the tensile strength of the composites.

Fig 5 Transmittance of PMMA/PA6 composites

Fig 7 Transmittance of PMMA/PA6/MWCNTs composites

Fig 6 Transmittance of PMMA/PA6/ TiO_2 composite, left: TiO_2 added in the shell part; right: TiO_2 added in the core part

In this work, pure PA-6 and pure PMMA nanofiber membranes made by single-phase electrospinning were laid alternatively into the mold and hot pressed into composites. This kind of composites was somewhat similar to those reported in Ref. [3, 4], but was obtained with different processing method. Mechanical properties of thus obtained nanofiber membranes-reinforced PMMA composites were compared with those of the nanofiber reinforced composites by making use of co-axial electrospinning and were shown in **Fig. 9**. It is seen that the tensile strength of the nanofiber membranes-reinforced composites was higher than that of the pure PMMA panel, but lower than the tensile strength of the nanofiber-reinforced composites. This difference could be attributed to the difference in interfaces between different systems. The PA-6 nanofibers and PMMA matrix had a better interface bounding with the coaxially electrospun core/shell structure.

Fig 11 shows the fracture surfaces of the two kinds of PMMA matrix composites. For the PA-6 nanofiber reinforced composites, many pullout nanofibers were observed on a failed surface. On the contrary, nanofibers membranes were adhered to the PMMA matrix on the fractured surface with apparent boundaries between the membranes and the matrix. Therefore, the boundaries between the PA-6 nanofiber membranes and the

matrix resulted in a weak interfacial adhesion and lowered down the tensile strength. When MWCNTs were added in the core part of the PMMA/PA-6 composite nanofibers, the MWCNTs were uniformly dispersed. Tensile strength of the resulting composites increased with an increase in mass percentage of MWCNTs, as shown in Fig. 10.

Fig 8 Tensile strength of PMMA/PA6 composites

Fig 9 Tensile strength of PMMA/PA6 composites with two kinds of PA6 reinforcement

Fig 10 Tensile strength of PMMA/PA6/MWCNTs composites

Fig 11 SEM photos of fractured surfaces of PMMA/PA-6 composites, a) with PA-6 nanofiber membranes as reinforcement, b) with PA-6 nanofibers as reinforcement

It has been known that a modification on the surface of a polymer fiber can enhance the mechanical performance of a composite made using this fiber as reinforcement. In the present case, however, the reinforcing PA-6 nanofiber was already made into the core part of a composite nanofiber. A UV light radiation was applied in this study to modify surface of the reinforcing PA-6 fibers within the electrospun PMMA/PA-6 composite nanofibers. Three different radiation periods of time were used to compare mechanical

properties of the resulting composites (**Table 1**). The tensile strength of the composites was improved slightly after a short time UV treatment, but lowered down when a UV treatment lasted for more than 1 hour. A UV absorber was used as an additive to eliminate a destructive effect of UV radiation on the composite nanofibers. The experiment data showed that the use of a UV absorber was slight in prevention of nanofiber degradation due to the UV damage. No noticeable change in mechanical properties was recognized for adding more than 2.0g UV absorbers.

Table 1 Tensile properties of PMMA/PA6 nanocomposites under UV treatment

PMMA/PA6	UV treatment			UV absorber (g/10g)		
	(no UV absorber)			Treating time:30min		
	15min	30min	60min	0.5g	1.0g	2.0g
Tensile strength /MPa	53.21	57.78	49.56	56.69	60.01	60.56
Tensile modulus/GPa	2.109	2.121	2.117	2.098	2.112	2.085

4. CONCLUSION

Co-axial electrospinning technique combined with hot process method was used to fabricate PMMA/PA-6, PMMA/PA-6/TiO₂ and PMMA/PA-6/MWCNTs nanofiber reinforced transparent composites. Through TEM and FTIR experiments, the presence of PA-6 or PA-6/TiO₂ core layer was demonstrated. Further affirmation on a uniform distribution of PA-6 nanofibers in the composite was gained by a fracture morphology analysis. Thermal stability and mechanical properties were improved with the addition of nanofibers.

The introduction of TiO₂ nanoparticles as a UV absorber to the PMMA/PA-6 nanocomposites showed a strong absorbing ability in the wavelength range of 230-400 nm. The TiO₂ nano-particles added in the shell part of the PMMA/PA-6 composite nanofibers exhibited a remarkable performance on absorbing UV light but a lower ability for a visible light transmittance. On the contrary, those added in the core part had a reversed effect on both UV and visible light transmittances. MWCNTs were well dispersed in the PMMA/PA-6 nanocomposites through coaxial electrospinning, and the tensile strength of the resulting PMMA/PA6/MWCNTs nanocomposites was improved with an increase in a mass percentage of MWCNTs within the range considered in this work.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research is partially financially supported by the National Natural Science Foundations of China with a grant number of 50773054.

References

1. Chunyi Tang, Haiqing Liu. Cellulose nanofiber reinforced poly(vinyl alcohol) composite film with high visible light transmittance. *Composites: Part A* 2008, 39: 1638-1643
2. Masaya Nogi, Keishin Handa, Antonio Norio Nakagaito, Hiroyuki Yano. Optically transparent bionanofiber. *Composites with low sensitivity to refractive index of the polymer matrix. Applied Physics Letters* 2005, 87: 243100-1
3. Michel M Bergshoef, G Julius Vancso. Transparent nanocomposites with ultrathin,electrospun nylon-4, 6 nanofiber reinforcement. *Advanced materials* 1999, 16: 1362-1365
4. Hiroyuki Yano, Junji Sugiyama, Antonio Norio Nakagaito, Masaya Nogi, et al. Optically transparent composites reinforced with networks of bacterial nanofibers. *Advanced materials* 2005, 17 (2): 153-157
5. Yeseul Kim, Rira Jung, Hun-Sik Kim, Hyoung-Joon Jin. Transparent nanocomposites prepared by incorporating microbial nanofibrils into poly(L-lactic acid). *Current Applied Physics* 2009, 9: 569-571
6. Guanfushou Chen, Haiqing Liu. Electrospun Cellulose Nanofiber Reinforced Soybean Protein Isolate Composite Film. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 2008, 110: 641-646
7. Dale W Schaefer, Ryan S. Justice. How nano are nanocomposites? *Macromolecules* 2007 40 (24): 8501-8517
8. Song Lin, Qing Cai, Jianying Ji, Gang Sui, Yunhua Yu, Xiaoping Yang, Qi. Ma, Yan Wei, Xuliang Deng. Electrospun nanofiber reinforced and toughened composites through in situ nano-interface formation. *Composites Science and Technology* 2008, 68: 3322-3329
9. Rene´ J. Nussbaumer, Walter R. Caseri, Paul Smith, Theo Tervoort. Polymer-TiO₂ nanocomposites: A route towards visually transparent broadband UV filter and high refractive index materials [J]. *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* 2003, 288: 44-49.
10. Jung-Kon Kim, Kyungho Choi, Il-Hyoung Cho. Application of a microbial toxicity assay for monitoring treatment effectiveness of pentachlorophenol in water using UV photolysis and TiO₂ photocatalysis. *Journal of Hazardous Materials.* 2007, 148(2): 281-286
11. Guangcan Xiao, Xinchun Wang, Danzhen Li. InVO₄-sensitized TiO₂ photocatalysts for efficient air purification with visible light. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry.* 2007, 193(3): 213-221
12. Lu-Song Chen, Zheng-Ming Huang, Guo-Hua Dong, Chuang-Long He, Ling Liu, Ying-Ying Hu, Yan Li. Development of a Transparent PMMA Composite Reinforced With Nanofibers. *Polymer composites* 2009, 40 (3): 239-247
13. R Pérez-Bustamante, C D Gómez-Esparza, I Estrada-Guel, M Miki-Yoshida, L Licea-Jiménez, S A Pérez-García, R Martínez-Sánchez. Microstructural and mechanical characterization of Al-MWCNT composites produced by mechanical milling. *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 2009, 502(1-2): 159-163